

A MICROMECHANICAL MODEL ON THE TENSILE STRESS-STRAIN RELATION AND STRENGTH OF SiCw/LD₂ COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Through in-situ TEM observation on tensile specimens of SiCw/LD₂ composite, it can be found that since the whisker length is much shorter than the critical length, some preferable whisker ends debond when tensile load is applied on the specimen. With increasing the load, more and more whisker ends debond from the matrix. By considering the damage evaluation and the plastic deformation of the matrix, a stress-strain relation of composite has been obtained based on the solution of a system of differential equations for the stress of matrix and inhomogeneities and the density of fiber-end cracks. when the load reaches some critical value, at least two neighboring fiber-end cracks coalesce, and it leads to the rupture of the material. As a consequence, the two-crack-coalescence model was developed to predict the strength of SiCw/LD₂ composite.

INTRODUCTION

It is a well-known fact that some metal matrix composites such as SiCw/LD₂ have a much higher strength and very strong hardening effect under the tensile loading. To understand the overall properties of the composite based on some microstructural quantities is very important for improving the existed materials and developing new materials. Through in-situ TEM observation on tensile specimen of 23vol%SiCw/LD₂ composite, it can be found that since the whisker length is much shorter than the critical length, some preferable whisker ends debond when tensile load is applied on the specimen, and the crack propagation into the matrix is prohibited due to the strong hardening effect of the matrix. Based on such observation, the debonding damage is controlled by the stress just outside the whiskers and the statistical behavior of the whisker-matrix interfacial strength. Since the ductile matrix can deform plastically under the applied loading, a coupled system of differential equation has been established and solved simultaneously for the stress of matrix and inhomogeneities, and the density of fiber-end cracks. Based on the solution of the stress inside the inclusion and in the matrix, the stress-strain relation can be derived easily. With increasing the load, more

and more whisker ends debond from the matrix. When the load reaches some critical value, at least two neighbouring fiber-end cracks coalesce. As the consequence of the coalescence, more and more microcracks will coalesce, and form a macroscopic crack, then lead to the fracture of the material without need to increase the applied load. Based on the observation, two-crack-coalescence model was developed to predict the strength of SiCw/LD2 composite, and it is found that the prediction is in good agreement with the experimental data.

THE INCREMENTAL STRESS OF MATRIX AND INHOMOGENEITIES

Consider an infinite elastoplastic body containing infinite number of ellipsoidal inhomogeneities and subjected to the applied stress σ^0 . The average number of inclusions in unit volume is $n = C_I/v_0$, where C_I is the volume fraction of the inhomogeneities, v_0 is the average volume of a single inclusion. At the external load σ^0 , there are m inhomogeneities which have been debonded from the matrix at the end, i. e. there are m fiber-end cracks. Due to the existence of the fiber-end cracks, the load inside the neighbouring inclusions should be different from those inclusions which contain no fiber-end cracks. In the work of Takao et al⁽⁴⁾, the damaged fibers are assumed to have shorter effective length than perfect fibers. In our work, for simplicity, we take two extreme cases into consideration. One case is that the fibers play no fiber's role if they contain the fiber-end cracks, i. e. with increasing the fiber-end cracks, the volume fraction of fibers is reduced. The other case is that the fiber-end cracks only make the matrix softer. With above assumption, to derive the incremental stress of matrix and inhomogeneities, we only need to consider the following problem: there are n or $(n-m)$ inclusions in the softening matrix which contains m microcracks, and the whole body is subjected to the applied stress σ^0 . If the tangential stiffness of the microcrack-containing matrix is L_1 , which can be obtained by considering a dilute distribution of penny shaped cracks embeded in plastic matrix, the tangential stiffness of the inhomogeneities is L_2 , according to the Mori-Tanaka method and the equivalent inclusion theory⁽³⁾, the incremental stress inside the matrix and the inhomogeneities can be written as

$$d\sigma_1 = d\sigma^0 + d\sigma_M \tag{1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d\sigma_2 = d\sigma^0 + d\sigma_I &= L_1[L_1^{-1}(d\sigma^0 + d\sigma_M) + d\epsilon - d\epsilon^*] \\ &= L_2[L_1^{-1}(d\sigma^0 + d\sigma_M) + d\epsilon] \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where $d\sigma^0$ is the incremental applied load, $d\sigma_M$ and $d\sigma_I$ are incremental stress disturbances of matrix and inhomogeneities, respectively. The expressions (1) and (2) mean that the incremental strain before introducing inhomogeneities is $L_1^{-1}(d\sigma^0 + d\sigma_M)$. When the inhomogeneities has an ellipsoidal shape, the incremental strain is given by

$$d\epsilon = Sd\epsilon^* \tag{3}$$

where S is Eshelby's tensor⁽¹⁾ (Eshelby, 1957). The total incremental stress disturbance is zero

$$(1 - C_f)d\sigma_M + C_f d\sigma_I = 0 \tag{4}$$

From equations (2), (3) and (4), the incremental stress disturbances of matrix and inhomogeneities are obtained as

$$d\sigma_M = -C_f L_1 (S - I) d\epsilon^* \quad (5)$$

$$d\sigma_I = (1 - C_f) L_1 (S - I) d\epsilon^* \quad (6)$$

where I is the unity tensor. Substituting (5), (6) and (3) into (2), and solving for $d\epsilon^*$, we have the incremental eigenstrain

$$d\epsilon^* = [(1 - C_f)(L_2 - L_1)S - C_f(L_1 - L_2) + L_1]^{-1} \times (L_1 - L_2)L_1^{-1} d\sigma_0 \quad (7)$$

Knowing the incremental eigenstrain, we can easily obtain the incremental stress of the matrix and the inhomogeneities as follows

$$d\sigma_1 = d\sigma^\circ + d\sigma_M = D_M d\sigma^\circ \quad (8)$$

where

$$D_M = \{I - C_f L_1 (S - I) [(1 - C_f)(L_2 - L_1)S - C_f(L_1 - L_2) + L_1]^{-1} (L_1 - L_2)L_1^{-1}\} \quad (9)$$

and

$$d\sigma_2 = d\sigma^\circ + d\sigma_I = D_I d\sigma^\circ \quad (10)$$

where

$$D_I = \{I + (1 - C_f)L_1(S - I) [(1 - C_f)(L_2 - L_1)S - C_f(L_1 - L_2) + L_1]^{-1} (L_1 - L_2)L_1^{-1}\} \quad (11)$$

One must bear in mind that in derivation of equations (8) and (10), we assume that the number m of fiber-end cracks keeps constant when the applied load has an increment $d\sigma^\circ$. Therefore

$$D_M = \frac{\partial \sigma_1}{\partial \sigma_0} \quad (12)$$

$$D_I = \frac{\partial \sigma_2}{\partial \sigma_0} \quad (13)$$

If the number of fiber-end cracks increases dm , when the applied load has an increment $d\sigma^\circ$, the incremental stress of the matrix and the inhomogeneities can be expressed in the form as

$$d\sigma_1 = D_M d\sigma^\circ + \int_0^{\sigma} \frac{\partial D_M}{\partial m} d\sigma^\circ dm \quad (14)$$

$$d\sigma_2 = D_I d\sigma^\circ + \int_0^{\sigma} \frac{\partial D_I}{\partial m} d\sigma^\circ dm \quad (15)$$

where the increment of the number of fiber-end cracks will be determined in the

following part. Applying the relation $d\bar{\epsilon} = (1 - C_f)L_1^{-1}d\sigma_1 + C_fL_2^{-1}d\sigma_2$, the incremental stress-strain relation of the composite can be determined easily.

KINETIC EQUATIONS OF DAMAGE EVOLUTION

According to in-situ TEM observation of the initiation and growth of microcracks in SiCw/ LD2 during tension deformation, the fiber-end cracking is a significant damage process in such material. Therefore in this paper, it was assumed that the cracking process is controlled by the stress in the matrix just outside the fiber and the statistical behavior of the fiber-matrix interfacial strength, i. e. when the maximum tensile stress in the matrix just outside the fiber is larger than the interfacial strength, a penny-shaped crack with definite length c will appear at the fiber-end. Due to the randomness of the interfacial strength, the damaging process is a random process with increasing load. To establish the evolutionary damage model, we introduce the following assumptions, (1) If there are x ($x=0,1,\dots,n$) fiber-end cracks in unit volume at the applied load σ° , when the applied load increases from σ° to $\sigma^\circ + \Delta\sigma^\circ$, the probability that one fiber in unit volume debonds at the end is $\lambda(x, \sigma^\circ)\Delta\sigma^\circ + o(\Delta\sigma^\circ)$. (2) When the applied load increases from σ° to $\sigma^\circ + \Delta\sigma^\circ$, the probability that more than one fiber-end cracks appear in unit volume is $o(\Delta\sigma^\circ)$. (3) The probability that no fiber-end crack appears for the incremental load is $1 - \lambda(x, \sigma^\circ)(N - x)\Delta\sigma^\circ + o(\Delta\sigma^\circ)$. Therefore, the probability $P_x(\sigma^\circ + \Delta\sigma^\circ)$ that there are x fiber-end cracks in unit volume at the external load $\sigma^\circ + \Delta\sigma^\circ$ can be expressed in the form as

$$P_x(\sigma^\circ + \Delta\sigma^\circ) = [1 - \lambda(x, \sigma^\circ)(N - x)\Delta\sigma^\circ]P_x(\sigma^\circ) + (N - x + 1)\lambda(x - 1, \sigma^\circ)P_{x-1}(\sigma^\circ)\Delta\sigma^\circ + O(\Delta\sigma^\circ) \tag{16}$$

By moving the term which contains $P_x(\sigma^\circ)$ to the left side, dividing by $\Delta\sigma^\circ$, and taking the limit $\Delta\sigma^\circ \rightarrow 0$, it is obtained

$$\frac{dP_x(\sigma^\circ)}{d\sigma^\circ} = -\lambda(x, \sigma^\circ)(N - x)P_x(\sigma^\circ) + \lambda(x - 1, \sigma^\circ)(N - x + 1)P_{x-1}(\sigma^\circ) \tag{17}$$

When $x=0$, $P_{x-1}(\sigma^\circ)=0$, therefore

$$\frac{dP_x(\sigma^\circ)}{d\sigma^\circ} = -\lambda(0, \sigma^\circ)NP_x(\sigma^\circ) \tag{18}$$

If the average number of fibers in unit volume is denoted as N , the incremental average number of fiber-end cracks in unit volume can be expressed in the form as

$$\Delta m = \lambda(m, \sigma^\circ)(N - m)\Delta\sigma^\circ \tag{19}$$

By taking the limit $\Delta\sigma^\circ \rightarrow 0$, one obtains

$$\frac{dm}{d\sigma^\circ} = (N - m)\lambda(m, \sigma^\circ) \tag{20}$$

Substitution of equation (19) into equations (14) and (15) yields

$$\frac{d\sigma_1}{d\sigma^0} = D_m + \lambda(m, \sigma^0)(N - m) \int_0^{\sigma^0} \frac{\partial D_M}{\partial m} d\sigma^0 \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{d\sigma_2}{d\sigma^0} = D_l + \lambda(m, \sigma^0)(N - m) \int_0^{\sigma^0} \frac{\partial D_l}{\partial m} d\sigma^0 \quad (22)$$

Equations (20), (21) and (22) are a system of simultaneous differential equations, and could be solved with the initial conditions

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = m = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad \sigma^0 = 0 \quad (23)$$

For different material microstructures, the intensity function $\lambda(x, \sigma^0)$ can be determined by determining the probability that one fiber in unit volume debonds at the end when the applied load increases from σ^0 to $\sigma^0 + \Delta\sigma^0$. For example, at the uniaxial loading $\sigma_{33}^0 \neq 0$, it is assumed that the debonding of the fiber is controlled by the maximum interfacial tensile stress and the statistical behavior of the interfacial strength. Furthermore, the following Weibull distribution is adopted for the cumulative probability of the interfacial debonding

$$F(\sigma_{33}^I) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma_{33}^I}{S_0}\right)^m\right] \quad (24)$$

where S_0 and m are the scale parameter and the shape parameter, respectively, and σ_{33}^I is the stress component inside the inclusion. In writing eqn (24), one should bear in mind that $\bar{\sigma}_{33} = \sigma_{33}^I$, where $\bar{\sigma}_{33}$ is the stress component just outside the fiber. Therefore, the intensity function $\lambda(x, \sigma^0)$ is given by

$$\lambda(x, \sigma^0) = \frac{\partial F}{\partial \sigma_{33}^I} \cdot \frac{\partial \sigma_{33}^I}{\partial \sigma_{33}^0} \quad (25)$$

To solve the system of differential equations (20), (21) and (22), one should substitute the tangential modulus of the matrix and fiber, which are functions of σ_1 and σ_2 , respectively, into these equations.

THE STRENGTH MODEL

For the SiCw/LD2 composite, since the yield stress and the work-hardening rate of the matrix is higher than some other composite system, e. x. SiCw/Al composite, the failure mechanism is mainly due to fiber-end debonding and the microcracks coalescing abruptly at some critical load to lead to the final rupture of the material. The crack propagation process is less important. In this paper, we introduce the two-crack-coalescence model, i. e. the occurrence of two fiber-end cracks coalescence is the failure criterion for composites.

Consider two co-planar penny shaped cracks with radius c under uniaxial tension, the stress intensity factor is given by ⁽²⁾

$$K_I = \frac{2}{\pi} \sigma_0 \sqrt{\pi c} \left[1 + \frac{1}{12\pi} \left(\frac{c}{r}\right)^3\right] \quad (26)$$

where $2r$ is the distance between the two centers of cracks, which is a random variable depending on the density of microcracks. According to Wang and Duan^[5] (1992), the probability density function of minimum distance between two fiber-end cracks is given by

$$f(r) = -16\pi N r^2 \log\left(1 - \frac{m}{N}\right) \left(1 - \frac{m}{N}\right)^{\frac{32}{3} \pi N (r^3 - c^3)} \quad (27)$$

Where $N = 0.74/\frac{4}{3}\pi C^3$, m is the average number of fiber-end cracks in unit volume. Therefore, the two-crack-coalescence-failure-criterion can be expressed in the form as

$$\langle K_I \rangle \geq K_{IC} \quad (28)$$

where $\langle K_I \rangle$ is the mean value of K_I , and K_{IC} is the critical value of the stress intensity factor of the matrix.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

In order to verify the theory, numerical analyses of the overall stress-strain response of 23vol% SiCw/LD2 composite under uniaxial tension were demonstrated. The matrix is LD2 alloy which contains 0.2–0.6% Cu, 0.45–0.9% Mg, 0.15–0.35Cr, 0.5–1.2%Si, and Al. The reinforcement is β -SiC whisker. The properties of β -SiC whisker and the alloys are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The properties of β -SiC whisker and the Al-alloys

Material	d, μm	l, μm	$\sigma_{0.2}$, Mpa	σ_b , Gpa	E, Gpa	K_{IC} , MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$
β -SiCw	0.1–1	30–100	—	3–14	400–700	—
LD2	—	—	280	0.32	71	45

The experimental results of the work-hardening rate versus true plastic strain for LD2 and their composites are shown in Fig. 1. The tangential stiffness of the matrix can be obtained from Fig. 1 and the whiskers are treated as elastic material during the whole deformation process. As a debonding property of the whisker-matrix interface, the Weibull distribution (24) is assumed, and the two parameters $S_0 = 320\text{MPa}$ and $m = 5$ are taken. The experimental result of tensile strength for 23vol% SiCw/LD2-T6 composite is 880 MPa, and the theoretical prediction based on the two-crack-coalescence-model gives the strength value 865MPa under the condition that the diameter of fiber-end penny shaped crack is double the size of whisker's diameter. The predicted and experimental results of the stress-strain relation are shown in Fig. 2.

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China.

REFERENCES

1. J. D. Eshelby, The determination of elastic field of an ellipsoidal inclusion and related problems, Proc. R. Soc. (London)A241, 376-396(1957).
2. M. Kachanov, A simple technique of stress analysis in elastic solid with many cracks, Int. J. of Fracture. 28, R11-R19(1985).
3. S. C. Lin, Y. Hirose and T. Mura, Constitutive equations of power-law composites and failure of materials having multiple cracks, ASME Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology, vol. 116, 359-366(1994).
4. Y. Takao, M. Taya and T. W. Chou, Effects of fiber-end cracks on the stiffness of aligned short-fiber composites, Int. J. Soids Structures, vol. 8, 723-728 (1982).
5. B. Wang and Z. P. Duan, The strength distribution of brittle materials with a high concentration of cavities, Engng. Fract. Mech. vol. 43, No. 1, (1992).

Fig. 1 Work-hardening rate vs. true plastic strain for LD2 and their composites.

Fig.2 The true stress vs. true strain curves of LD2 materials and their composites.

